

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF COMPOUND WORDS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation. This study analyzes the similarities and differences in the formation of compound words in English and Uzbek languages. The spelling of compound words in these languages is reviewed and explained more clearly with examples.

The examples are taken from English and Uzbek literature and help to learn more about compound words in both languages. The purpose of the study is to show the peculiarities of the use of these Uzbek and English compound words.

Key words: compound verb, compound noun, compound adjective, word formation, punctuation.

Аннотация. В данном исследовании анализируются сходства и различия в образовании сложных слов в английском и узбекском языках. Написание сложных слов в этих языках рассмотрено и более наглядно объяснено на примерах.

Примеры взяты из английской и узбекской литературы и помогают больше узнать о сложных словах на обоих языках. Цель исследования – показать особенности употребления этих узбекских и английских сложных слов.

Ключевые слова: составной глагол, составное существительное, составное прилагательное, словообразование, пунктуация.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi qo'shma so'zlarning yasalishidagi o'xshashliklar va farqli jihatlarni tahlil qilinadi. Bu tillardagi qo'shma so'zlarning yozilishi ko'rib chiqiladi va misollar bilan yanada aniqroq tushuntirib beriladi.

Misollar ingliz va o'zbek adabiyotlaridan olingan bo'lib, ikkala tildagi qo'shma so'zlarni chuqurroq o'rganishga yordam beradi. Tadqiqotdan maqsad ushbu o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi qo'shma so'zlarni qo'llashdagi o'ziga xosliklarni ko'rsatib berish.

Tayanch so'zlar: qo'shma fe'l, qo'shma ot, qo'shma sifat, so'z yasalishi, ajratib yozish.

In the branch of lexicology, when we study one of the compound words according to the structure of the studied word, compound words in both languages are compared and their similarities are analyzed. It can be said that compound words are a part of enriching the language, because the speech comes out beautiful and unique through compound words. When we use compound words in our speech, we are interested in how specific they are and how they are used in other languages. English and Uzbek are languages rich in compound words. In them, we can see different forms of compound words. One of the main differences is in their writing and construction, which we will now consider with examples.

Formation of compound verbs in Uzbek:

1. **Compound verbs in the noun + verb structure** ¹: "-Sezyapman, otajon, sezyapman. Yana jim bo'lamiz²"

¹ O'zbek tilidan ma'ruzalar to'plami / N. Erkaboyeva.-T.: «Yosh kuch», 2023. p 408

Here the compound verb is formed with the word "jim bo'lmoq". 2. **Compound verbs in the verb + verb structure**³:

"Hammamizni cho'ntagimizga to'ldirib yong'oq solib beradi"⁴ .
Here, "solib bermoq" is a compound verb.
We looked at the formation of compound verbs in the Uzbek language and their use in sentences.
Forming compound verbs in English⁵: Verb + preposition.
"Look at your hands, look at your mouth"⁶.

Look-verb is made in the form of at-preposition and has one general translation in Uzbek. In conclusion, we can say that it is difficult to find the same translation for verbs in English and Uzbek languages, because words that act as compound verbs in English can be equivalent to one simple word in Uzbek. But the noun from other word groups is translated literally and acts as a compound word in both languages. For example, snowman-qorbobo.

With this example, we can see that not all nouns have such a translation, but more often than verbs, they are translated in the form of compound noun - compound noun.

The main difference between compound verbs in English and Uzbek: compound verbs in Uzbek can be used independently. But the second part of compound verbs in the English language can not come independently, because the second part means a whole with the first part. In terms of structure, the meaning of a compound verb is equal to one word. We tried to show the differences and similarities of English and Uzbek words through these examples.

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² Jannati odamlar/Ertak-roman.X. To'xtaboyev. -T.: «Yangi asr avlodi», 2018. – p 1

³ O'zbek tilidan ma'ruzalar to'plami / N. Erkaboyeva.-T.: «Yosh kuch», 2023. p 410

⁴ Jannati odamlar/Ertak-roman.X. To'xtaboyev. -T.: «Yangi asr avlodi», 2018. – p 21

⁵ Simon Clarke, Macmillian English Grammar in Context. London.: Holtzbrinck Publishing Group.

2008, p 146 ⁶ Mark Twain, Tom Sawyer. America.: American publishing company. 1884, p.